

Syllabus Introduction to in silico medicine for non-engineers

1. Introduction

The learning goals indicate the requirements of each lecture of the course 'Introduction to in silico medicine for non-engineers' (3 ECTS). Based on these requirements the instructors can format their lecture based on their own teaching preferences, knowledge and experience, while ensuring a qualitative introductory course on in silico medicine. Note that some learning goals are formulated for more than one lecture. This does not mean that the learning goals should be achieved in each of these lectures. It is the aim that the learning goals are achieved in at least one of the lectures, but how they are distributed over the lectures is up to the preferences of the instructor.

2. Overview lectures and exercise sessions

Week	Lecture (1h)	Topic lecture	Exercise session (2h)	Topic exercise session
1	L01	Recall concepts of biostatistics – Part I		
2	L02	Recall concepts of biostatistics - Part II	P01	Recall concepts of biostatistics
3	L03	Introduction to bioengineering - Part I		
4	L04	Introduction to bioengineering - Part II	P02	Introduction to bioengineering
5	L05	Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?		
6	L06	From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare	P03	From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare
7	L07	Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part I		
8	L08	Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part II		
9	L09	Clinical applications of in silico medicine	P04	Examples of in silico medicine: experimentation and clinical applications
10	L10	In silico medicine: ethical and social considerations	P05	In silico medicine: ethical and social considerations
11	L11	Communication in interdisciplinary settings		
12	L12	Communication to patients	P06	Communication in interdisciplinary settings (including patients)

3. Lectures

L01: Recall concepts of biostatistics - Part I

Applicable ILOs

H1.3.5: Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments

H1.1.7: Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data

Learning goals

- *Explain the concepts of probability, random variables and probability distributions and illustrate them based on examples within the domain of biology;*
- *Elucidate the difference between population and sample statistics;*
- *Calculate the sample mean, median and variance from a given set of data;*
- *Explain the concept of hypothesis testing and confidence interval in their own words;*
- *Distinguish between observations, experiments and randomized controlled trials and their impact on the conclusions that can be drawn from statistical analysis;*
- *Select appropriate graphs to represent data and its distribution.*

L02: Recall concepts of biostatistics - Part II

Applicable ILOs

H1.3.5: Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments

H1.1.7: Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data

Learning goals

- *Explain the concepts of probability, random variables and probability distributions and illustrate them based on examples within the domain of biology;*
- *Elucidate the difference between population and sample statistics;*
- *Calculate the sample mean, median and variance from a given set of data;*
- *Explain the concept of hypothesis testing and confidence interval in their own words;*
- *Distinguish between observations, experiments and randomized controlled trials and their impact on the conclusions that can be drawn from statistical analysis;*
- *Select appropriate graphs to represent data and its distribution.*

L03: Introduction to bioengineering - Part I

Applicable ILOs

H1.4.1: Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.2: Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.3: Select appropriate in vitro diagnostics instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.4: Elaborate bio-signals and medical images

Learning goals

- *Explain the general working principles of biomedical instrumentation that is commonly used in the clinical practice;*
- *Identify appropriate biomedical instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case and explain its global working principle;*
- *Explain the general working principles of clinically used medical imaging techniques, such as computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging and ultrasound;*
- *Identify appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case;*
- *Explain the general working principles of in vitro diagnostics instrumentation that is commonly used in clinical laboratories;*
- *Identify appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case.*

L04: Introduction to bioengineering - Part II

Applicable ILOs

H1.4.1: Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.2: Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.3: Select appropriate in vitro diagnostics instrumentation to obtain the desired information

H1.4.4: Elaborate bio-signals and medical images

Learning goals

- *Explain the general working principles of biomedical instrumentation that is commonly used in the clinical practice;*
- *Identify appropriate biomedical instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case and explain its global working principle;*
- *Explain the general working principles of clinically used medical imaging techniques, such as computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging and ultrasound;*
- *Identify appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case;*

- *To explain the general working principles of in vitro diagnostics instrumentation that is commonly used in clinical laboratories;*
- *To identify appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case.*

L05: Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?

Applicable ILOs

NA

Learning goals

- *Understand the complexity of dealing with predictions about human health;*
- *Identify the origins of barriers against adoption of in silico technologies (complexity, redundancy, stochasticity, culture);*
- *Summarize first examples of digital twins and in silico trials developed;*
- *Assess the value of the in silico trials in the development of new medical products;*
- *Outline the 3R concept that led in silico trials;*
- *Illustrate how in silico technologies might be of help to ensure and extend the healthcare, given how the world population is growing;*
- *Explain what the virtual human twin will be.*

L06: From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare

Applicable ILOs

H2.2: Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication

H2.12: Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

Learning goals

- *Formulate a definition of a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Summarize the potential benefits of using a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Clarify the main challenges to integrate in silico medicine in the current clinical practice;*
- *Identify the subsequent steps of the workflow that translates a clinical problem to a digital twin;*
- *Give two examples of existing clinical problems that could benefit from in silico medicine.*

L07: Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part I

Applicable ILOs

H4.1: Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

Learning goals

- *Give three examples of in silico medicine that have been used to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and human experimentation;*
- *Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of replacing and/or refining in vitro, animal and human experiments by in silico medicine;*
- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and/or human experimentation for a given case study.*

L08: Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation - Part II

Applicable ILOs

H4.1: Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

Learning goals

- *Give three examples of in silico medicine that have been used to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and human experimentation;*
- *Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of replacing and/or refining in vitro, animal and human experiments by in silico medicine;*
- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and/or human experimentation for a given case study.*

L09: Clinical applications of in silico medicine

Applicable ILOs

H2.12: Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

Learning goals

- *Summarize three state-of-the-art applications of in silico medicine used in clinical practice;*
- *Evaluate the added value of a given clinical application of in silico medicine to the clinical practice;*

- *Identify which aspects of a given clinical application of in silico medicine require optimization to improve the clinical application.*

L10: In silico medicine: ethical and social considerations

Applicable ILOs

H2.5: Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication

H2.6: Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies to the public and patients

Learning goals

- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from an ethical perspective and illustrate arguments with example cases;*
- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from a social perspective and illustrate arguments with example cases.*

L11: Communication in interdisciplinary settings

Applicable ILOs

H2.1: Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies

H2.2: Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication

Learning goals

- *Explain technical terms such as segmentation, registration, meshing and in silico modeling in layman's terms;*
- *Identify how in silico models can contribute to a given clinical need;*
- *Formulate the benefits and drawbacks of an in silico model based on communication with healthcare professionals.*

L12: Communication to patients

Applicable ILO's

H2.8: Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients

Learning goals

- *Explain the workflow to develop an in silico model starting from medical imaging of the patients in layman's terms;*
- *Formulate the general working principle of an in silico model in layman's terms;*
- *Formulate the benefits and limitations of the use of in silico models in optimizing the patient-specific diagnosis or treatment for a given clinical problem.*

4. Exercise sessions

The learning goals indicated in grey correspond to learning goals that have also been formulated for the lectures. By pursuing the same learning goal in a different context (e.g. understanding an example during the lecture and applying a concept during the exercise session), a better understanding of the considered aspect is expected.

P01: Recall concepts of biostatistics

Description

The students receive a dataset, with input and output data, of a clinical experiment that compares different treatments. The students perform an exploratory data analysis on the dataset, which includes plotting of the input and output data and calculation of sample mean, median and variance of the dataset. Afterwards, a significance test on the data is performed. It is important that the focus on the experiment (e.g. observations vs. randomized controlled trials), the assumptions and the interpretation of the test, rather than on performing the test.

Learning goals

- *Calculate the sample mean, median and/or variance from a given set of data;*
- *Distinguish between observations, experiments and randomized controlled trials and their impact on the conclusions that can be drawn from statistical analysis;*
- *Select appropriate graphs to represent data and its distribution.*

P02: Introduction to bioengineering

Description

Rather than a classical exercise session, a more practically hands-on session in which the students can familiarize themselves with the biomedical and in vitro diagnostics instrumentation is strongly recommended. The students get the opportunity to see some of the instruments discussed during the lecture in real-life. In the first part of the session, the students get a demo of the different instruments and a recap of their general working principles, input and output. Afterwards, the students are divided into groups and each group goes along all different biomedical instruments to gain some hands-on experience with the instrumentation (if possible). In the last part of the session, some example cases are given to the students and they are asked to suggest and argue which of the instruments would be recommended to collect the required data.

Learning goals

- *Identify appropriate biomedical instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case and explain its global working principle;*

- *Identify appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to collect the required data for a given example case;*
- *Perform basic operations on some biomedical and in vitro diagnostics instrumentation.*

P03: From a clinical problem to a digital twin in healthcare

Description

Based on a case study from the clinical practice, preferably presented by the surgeon/clinician, the students determine the requirements and specifications for a digital twin. Afterwards, they develop a workflow that could be used to create such a digital twin (without really creating the digital twin themselves). In this process, the students are encouraged to think about the challenges related to the development of a digital twin and its use in clinical practice.

Learning goals

- *Summarize the potential benefits of using a digital twin in healthcare;*
- *Identify the subsequent steps of the workflow that translates a clinical problem to a digital twin;*
- *Clarify the challenges to integrate the in silico medicine in the current clinical practice related to a specific case study;*
- *Determine the global requirements and specifications for a digital twin based on a clinical case study.*

P04: Examples of in silico medicine: experimentation and clinical applications

Description

The students receive case studies of problem statements in experimentation. For each of these case studies, the students identify how in silico medicine can be applied to optimize the experimentation process and what the advantages and disadvantages are of using in silico medicine compared to the current golden standard methodologies. In the second part, an in silico clinical application is provided to the students, with given specifications of an in silico model. The students study the specifications and discuss the added value and points of improvement of the given model.

Learning goals

- *Identify how in silico medicine can be applied to replace and/or refine in vitro, animal and/or human experimentation for a given case study.*
- *Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of replacing and/or refining in vitro, animal and human experiments by in silico medicine;*
- *Evaluate the added value of a given clinical application of in silico medicine to the clinical practice;*

- *Identify which aspects of a given clinical application of in silico medicine require optimization to improve the clinical application.*

P05: In silico medicine: ethical and social considerations

Description

The students receive an authentic case study with a proposal for an in silico model (for clinical or experimental application). The students critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of this in silico model from an ethical and social perspective. Based on this discussion, the student decide whether the proposed in silico model is acceptable or not and argue their decision.

Learning goals

- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from an ethical perspective for a given example case;*
- *Critically discuss the benefits and drawbacks of the use of in silico medicine from a social perspective for a given example case.*

P06: Communication in interdisciplinary settings (including patients)

Description

The students receive a written report of an expert in in silico methodologies, in which the expert compares the in silico model to the current golden standard treatment. The student read the report and extract the most important concepts. The students use this information to write a report on this in silico methodology and how it compares to the existing treatment in layman's terms to provide the information to patients.

Learning goals

- *Formulate the benefits and drawbacks of an in silico model based on communication with healthcare professionals.*
- *Formulate the general working principle of an in silico model in layman's terms;*
- *Formulate the benefits and limitations of the use of in silico models in optimizing the patient-specific diagnosis or treatment for a given clinical problem.*